

Thermal design and heat transfer optimisation of a Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carrier batch reactor for hydrogen storage

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ABSTRACT

Liquid organic hydrogen carriers (LOHCs) are considered a promising hydrogen storage technology. Heat must be exchanged with an external medium, such as an external fluid, for the required chemical reactions to occur. Batch reactors are simple but useful solutions for small-scale storage applications, which can be modelled with a lumped-parameter approach, adequately reproducing their dynamic performance. For such reactors, power is consumed to circulate the external heat transfer fluid and stir the organic liquid inside the reactor, and heat transfer performance and power consumption are two key parameters in reactor optimisation. Therefore, with reference to the hydrogen release phase, this paper describes a procedure to optimise the reactor thermal design, based on a lumped-parameter model, in terms of heat transfer performance and minimum power consumption. Two batch reactors are analysed: a conventional jacketed reactor with agitation nozzles and a half-pipe coil reactor. Heat transfer efficacy is evaluated by introducing a newly defined dimensionless parameter, the Heat Transfer Ratio (HTR), whose value directly correlates to the heat rate required by the carrier's dehydrogenation reaction. The resulting model is a valid tool for adequately reproducing the hydrogen storage behaviour within dynamic models of complex and detailed energy systems.

1. Introduction

The development of reliable and competitive hydrogen technologies has been considered fundamental by nations all over the world, such as Japan [1], China [2], the UK [3], the USA [4], and EU members [5]. For the latter, a strong emphasis has been placed in recent months in response to the Ukrainian-Russian crisis [6]. Today, more than ever, reducing the influence of fossil fuels is mandatory to preserve our climate, our planet, and economic and social stability.

Although sustainable hydrogen production and hydrogen-based technologies still require further research [7], hydrogen storage brings additional issues that need to be addressed, such as safety hazards and low energy density [8]. Traditionally, the two main pathways to store hydrogen are compressed [9] and liquid hydrogen [10], but both are lacklustre in terms of energy density, storage conditions, and efficiency. Consequently, alternative routes have been explored, such as Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carriers (LOHCs): in these molecules, double carbon-carbon bonds are reversibly broken to store hydrogen through exothermic reactions (hydrogenation). On the contrary, to release hydrogen, endothermic reactions must occur (dehydrogenation) as the double bonds are reformed [11].

LOHCs were first proposed in the 1980s [12], although they have gained popularity only in the last few years [13].

Currently, Di-Benzyl-Toluene (DBT) [14] and N-Ethyl-Carbazole (NEC) [15] are the candidates most studied, although a multitude of other fluids could also be used [16]. Research is still ongoing not only for a carrier, but also for better catalysts [17], which are arguably mainly important during dehydrogenation [18] as higher temperatures are needed, and slow kinetics can prevent deep discharges [19, 20], while the end-user requirements must be respected.

Although research on the chemistry of the process is still actively pursued, different case studies have been analysed to evaluate the performance of complex systems based on hydrogen turbines [21], or fuel cells [22]. Both papers focus mainly on the end-user application, but little information is reported about the actual behaviour of the carrier, allegedly modelled in 1D. Furthermore, the design proposed by Dennis et al. is characterised by an excessively cumbersome

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reactor [21]. On the contrary, Yang et al. focus on LOHC using a 2D model, although the influence of pressure on the reaction rate is omitted [23].

Although with different geometries, all the reactors mentioned above show a significant evolution of the degree of hydrogenation (DoH) in the axial direction with only moderate variation in the radial direction; consequently, they can be modelled as plug flow reactors (PFRs). This design is in line with the traditional tubular and shell-and-tube heat exchangers and is suitable for relatively high flow rates of discharged hydrogen. However, simpler reactors, modelled as batch reactors, can provide effective storage solutions for small-scale hydrogen-based energy systems, and are going to be required in a fully fledged hydrogen economy.

Therefore, the aim of this paper is to present a procedure to optimise the thermal design of LOHC-based batch reactors, ensuring the required heat exchange efficacy and the lowest power requirement. The former is assessed through a novel dimensionless parameter, the Heat Transfer Ratio (HTR), while the latter is evaluated as the combination of pumping and stirring consumption. Hence, this paper does not deal directly with the chemical and kinetic performance of the reactor, which are assumed to be known for the LOHC and catalyst by means of a characterisation resulting in a set of coefficients that can then be implemented in a model developed by the authors [24]. Instead, the focus here is on the thermal design of the reactor, and in particular on how to achieve the most efficient heat transfer process between the LOHC and the heat transfer fluid, taking into account the power consumption from the stirring of LOHC inside the reactor and the circulation of external fluid.

The resulting lumped-parameter model is particularly useful, notwithstanding some unavoidable loss of detail, because it adequately reproduces the overall dynamics, thus making it possible to build dynamic models of complex energy systems, of which LOHC-based hydrogen storage systems only represent a component. So, these findings will be the starting point for more in-depth characterisations, including end-user requirements and control strategies in batch reactors, and thermal design considerations for continuous reactors.

2. Methods

2.1. Kinetic and thermodynamic model

Most LOHC-based literature features a plug-flow reactor coupled with one-dimensional modelling to account for axial gradients. However, in a batch reactor, gradients are expected to arise mainly over the radial direction.

Both hydrogenation and dehydrogenation rates depend on temperature; heat is transferred to or from the system as the reactions occur. As a result, heat and mass transfers are mutually dependent in LOHC systems, as in MHs [25].

When heat is exchanged with the system through convection and propagated inside the system through conduction, the accuracy of a lumped parameter approach is usually estimated with the Biot number $Bi = hL/\lambda$. No experimental data are available for the conductivities of LOHCs at high temperatures; however, using the model provided by Berger Bioucas et al., the conductivity can be estimated as $\lambda \cong 0.09 \text{ W/(mK)}$ at approximately 480 K [26]. Even assuming low values of the convective heat transfer coefficient such as $h \cong 1 \text{ kW/(m}^2\text{K)}$, the Biot number is bounded to be much higher than one.

Nevertheless, a lumped-parameter approach is effective because the overall reaction heat depends on the temperature. If more hydrogen is released (higher temperature), more heat is sunk, thus slowing down the heating action ensured by the external liquid. This balancing mechanism allows for 0D modelling of MHs [25]. The derived ODE system can be solved with an explicit third-order Runge-Kutta scheme.

The reactions occurring within the reactor are represented in a lumped parameter model by the following equation [24]:

$$\frac{d\text{DoH}}{dt} = k_0 \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{RT}\right) \exp(bp) \text{DoH}^2 \quad (1)$$

Conversion from the degree of hydrogenation DoH and its time derivative to hydrogen mass and mass flow rate requires the introduction of the maximum gravimetric hydrogen density w and the LOHC overall mass M_{LOHC} , resulting in the following expression for hydrogen mass flow rate:

$$\dot{m}_{H_2} = wM_{LOHC} \frac{d\text{DoH}}{dt} = wM_{LOHC} k_0 \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{RT}\right) \exp(bp) \text{DoH}^2 \quad (2)$$

Energy conservation results in the following equation:

$$C_{T,tot} \dot{T} = \dot{m}_{H_2} [\Delta H_r + (c_p - c_v)(T - T_0)] + \dot{m}_f c_f [1 - \exp(-UA_{HX}/(\dot{m}_f c_f))], \quad (3)$$

Figure 1: Batch reactor designs; going from left to right: jacketed batch reactor and coiled batch reactor.

where the overall heat transfer coefficient is evaluated according to the equations described in the following section.

2.2. Reactor design

Heat is provided to the system through the reactor. In this paper, two alternative designs of a batch reactor were evaluated: jacketed and coiled reactors (Fig. 1), which differ in the way heat is provided to the system. The heat transfer correlations and the expected range of variability for each parameter were taken from Garvin, with reference to the conventional jacket with agitation nozzles and half-pipe coil designs [27].

As stated in the introduction, the optimisation process was conducted considering both the thermal efficacy of the reactor and the power consumption for the heat transfer fluid circulation and the LOHC stirring. The power requirements for the agitation nozzles were deemed negligible.

The global optimum was found through Matlab's Global Optimisation Tool.

2.2.1. Heat Transfer Ratio

The Heat Transfer Ratio (HTR), as defined in Eq. 4 and rewritten as Eq. 5, was deduced from the thermal balance to assess the efficacy of heat transfer. The HTR represents the ratio of the heat rate transferred by the external fluid, per unit temperature difference between the external fluid and the reactor, to the maximum heat rate generated by the dehydrogenation reaction, divided by the design temperature T_{des} to obtain a dimensionless quantity:

$$\text{HTR} = \frac{\dot{Q}_{ext.fluid}}{\dot{Q}_{reaction,max}} \cdot \frac{T_{des}}{T_{f,i} - T} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{HTR} = \frac{\dot{m}_f c_f \varepsilon}{\Delta H_r \dot{m}_{H_2,max} / T_{des}} \quad (5)$$

Therefore, the numerator is the product of heat transfer effectiveness ε and external fluid heat capacity $\dot{m}_f c_f$, while on the denominator side, the maximum heat rate depends on the heat of reaction ΔH_r and the maximum hydrogen flow rate, which is obtained at the beginning of the dehydrogenation process thanks to the highest value of DoH, provided that the reactor is heated to the desired reaction temperature beforehand, so that $T(t = t_0) = T_{des}$ (Eq. 2):

$$\dot{m}_{H_2,max} = \dot{m}_{H_2}(t = t_0) = w M_{LOHC} k_0 \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{RT_{des}}\right) \exp(bp) \text{DoH}_{max}^2 \quad (6)$$

By this definition, HTR can be used to assess the efficacy of heat transfer not only for different reactor sizes, but also for different LOHCs with similar reaction kinetic characteristics (for example, the same reaction order).

Alternative definitions of HTR were also tried. For example, the definition $HTR = \dot{m}_f c_f \epsilon / (m_{H_2} HHV)$ leads to an apparently much more straightforward parameterisation. The effective heat capacity is divided by the energy content of the system, thus removing sizing effects, but the resulting value is not dimensionless. More importantly, since different LOHCs vary in both release trends and reaction heat, the kinetic performances achieved with similar HTR for different carriers may lead to significantly different results.

Despite the more complex definition and the need to collect data on the kinetic release parameters, Eq. 5 was considered to be overall more significant due to the greater amount of information returned and the potential to be applied to different LOHCs.

To improve the efficacy of heat transfer, higher values of HTR can be achieved as:

- more heat is provided through a higher heat capacity of the external fluid, a better effectiveness of the exchanger, or both;
- the reaction temperature is set to a higher value;
- a reduced temperature drop takes place;
- less reaction heat is sunk.

Consequently, while the first two bullet points are likely detrimental in terms of the system's costs and overall efficiency, the remaining scenarios are actually desirable.

Finally, as discussed in Section 3, it should be noted that the HTR is introduced as a measure of the kinetic performances of a real LOHC system with respect to its corresponding constant-temperature equivalent system.

2.2.2. Design procedure

As for the actual sizing procedure, given the volume required to host the LOHC, for a given aspect ratio AR (Eq. 7), usually in the range of 1–4, both the height (H) and the inner diameter (D_{in}) of the batch can be evaluated (Eq. 8):

$$AR = H / D_{in} \quad (7)$$

$$V = \frac{\pi H^3}{4 AR^2}. \quad (8)$$

It should be noted that H is here defined in terms of the filling level, but the actual height of the reactor is likely to be somewhat higher to allow easier gas-liquid separation. Regardless, this upper empty space is almost unrelated to heat transfer performance and was then neglected in this analysis.

Having defined the wall thickness t_w (usually about 7 mm), the batch outer diameter is easily derived from the following equation:

$$D_e = D_{in} + 2t_w. \quad (9)$$

In the case of jacketed reactors, an additional diameter must be defined, that is, the outer diameter of the jacket D_j , which is evaluated as follows:

$$D_j = D_e + 2t, \quad (10)$$

where t is the thickness of the jacket, which is usually in the 20–50 mm range. The heat exchange area is instead given by:

$$A_{HX} = \pi D_e H, \quad (11)$$

while the cross section A_f available to the heat transfer fluid is obtained as:

$$A_f = H (D_j - D_e) / 2 \quad (12)$$

For coiled-pipe reactors, a tube diameter (d) should be chosen. Then, for a given pitch (s) representing the spacing between tubes, both the number of pipes (N_p) and the heat exchange surface (A_{HX}) are derived as follows:

$$N_p = \lfloor (H + s) / (d + s) \rfloor \quad (13)$$

$$A_{HX} = \pi D_e [(H - N_p d)\epsilon_f + N_p d] \quad (14)$$

The pitch is usually in the range 35–50 mm. Eq. 14 highlights that well-designed reactor coils act as fins and even the residual wall surface participates in heat transfer exchange with some efficiency. In this type of reactor, pipes do not have a circular section and are characterised by an angular opening (β). This value was set as 180°; another common value is 270°. Most pipes have a diameter in the range 5.08–10.16 cm (2–4 in). The cross section available to the heat transfer fluid is:

$$A_f = \frac{\pi d^2}{4} \beta N_p \quad (15)$$

Once the velocity v_f of the heat transfer fluid is set, usually in the range 0.50–1.50 m/s, the mass flow rate is given, for both types of reactor, by:

$$\dot{m}_f = \rho_f A_f v_f \quad (16)$$

Therefore, the effectiveness of heat transfer can be evaluated as a function of the Number of Transfer Units NTU as follows:

$$NTU = A_{HX} U / (\dot{m}_f c_f) \quad (17)$$

$$\epsilon = 1 - \exp(-NTU) \quad (18)$$

The overall heat transfer coefficient U in Eq. 17 accounts for the convective heat transfer from the external fluid to the batch reactor (h_f), conduction through the wall (λ_m) and, lastly, inner convection through the carrier (h_l).

$$U = \left(\frac{1}{h_f} + \frac{D_e \ln(D_e/D_i)}{2\lambda_m} + \frac{D_e}{D_i} \frac{1}{h_l} \right)^{-1} \quad (19)$$

Values of λ_m are given assuming a stainless steel 316L reactor; heat conductivity at working temperature is evaluated using data available in the literature [28].

The heat transfer coefficients in Eq. 19 are evaluated with empirical formulae for external fluid [27] and carrier [29], respectively.

In coiled reactors, the heat transfer coefficient of the external fluid is a function of the Reynolds number (evaluated through the hydraulic diameter d_{hyd}), the Prandtl number, and the ratio between the hydraulic and curvature diameters:

$$Nu_f = 0.0225 Re_f^{0.795} Pr_f^{0.495} \exp[-0.0225(\log Pr_f)^2] \left\{ 1 + 0.059 [Re_f (d_{hyd}/d_c)^2]^{0.34} \right\} \quad (20)$$

$$\alpha_c = \arctan \left(\frac{2H}{\pi D_{in}} \right) \quad (21)$$

$$d_c = D_{in} / \cos(\alpha_c) \quad (22)$$

In the case of jacketed reactors, the convective heat transfer coefficient can be estimated from empirical formulae as a function of the Reynolds number (evaluated through the hydraulic diameter d_{hyd}), the Prandtl number, and an entrance correction (Ge_f), as follows:

$$Nu_f = 0.0192 Re_f^{0.795} Pr_f^{0.495} \exp[-0.0225(\log Pr_f)^2] \left\{ 1 + 0.059 [Re_f (d_{hyd}/D_{in})^2]^{0.34} \right\} Ge_f \quad (23)$$

$$Ge_f = \begin{cases} 1, & Re_f (d_{hyd}/d_c)^2 \leq 4.72 \\ 1 + 5.71 \frac{d_{hyd}}{\pi D_e} [1 - \exp(1 - 0.07(\pi D_e)/d_{hyd})], & Re_f (d_{hyd}/d_c)^2 > 4.72. \end{cases} \quad (24)$$

On the contrary, heat transfer through the carrier adheres to the same mechanism in both reactors. Assuming natural convection to be negligible, h_l is evaluated from Eq. 25 ([29]). Since motion is related to angular velocity, the rotational Reynolds number (Re_ω) is introduced (Eq. 26).

$$Nu_l = 0.11 [(Re_\omega^2/2 + Gr)Pr_l]^{0.35} \quad (25)$$

$$\text{Re}_\omega = D_i^2 n \rho_l / (2\mu_l) \quad (26)$$

Due to the uniform heat exchange over the height of the reactor in the batch configuration, natural convection does not play any significant role in heat transfer. As such, the Grashof number (Gr) is set to zero. The rotational speed is evaluated through Eq. 37 as explained in the following paragraphs.

The pumping power requirement is evaluated from Eq. 27, having defined the concentrated pressure losses (Eq. 28) and the distributed pressure losses (Eq. 29) and the fanning friction factor, calculated either through Eq. 30 for jacketed reactors or Eq. 31 for coiled reactors:

$$P = \dot{m}_f (\Delta p_C + \Delta p_D) / \rho_f \quad (27)$$

$$\Delta p_C = 4K_{elbow} \rho_f v^2 / 2 \quad (28)$$

$$\Delta p_D = f \frac{\pi (D_e + d)}{d_{hyd}} \rho_f \frac{v^2}{2} \quad (29)$$

$$f = (1.8 \log_{10} \text{Re}^* - 1.5)^{-2} \quad (\text{jacketed reactors}) \quad (30)$$

$$f = \begin{cases} 16/\text{Re}, & 0 < \text{Re} < 2100 \\ 0.0791/\text{Re}^{0.25}, & 2100 \leq \text{Re} \leq 1 \times 10^7 \\ 0.0014 + 0.125/\text{Re}^{0.32}, & \text{Re} > 1 \times 10^7 \end{cases} \quad (\text{coiled reactors}). \quad (31)$$

The curvature effect is accounted for by the coefficient K_{elbow} in Eq. 28 as a tabulated value function of hydraulic and external diameter (d_{hyd}, D_e) for a 90° bending using data taken from White [30]. Regarding the Gnielinski correlation (Eq. 30), the value of Re^* must be evaluated as follows:

$$\text{Re}^* = \frac{[1 - (D_e/D_j)^2] + [(1 + D_e/D_i)^2] \log D_e/D_i}{[1 - (D_e/D_j)^2] \log D_e/D_j} \text{Re}. \quad (32)$$

It must also be noted that the hydraulic diameter defined for pressure loss evaluation is not the same as that required for heat transfer analysis, since the reference wet perimeter is different.

An impeller is required to mix the bulk liquid to promote homogeneity and improve the reaction operating conditions. Its power consumption scales with its diameter, rotational speed, LOHC density, and viscosity. This paper uses correlations available in the literature [31], assuming a Half Hold-up impeller:

$$d_{imp} = D_{in}/3 \quad (33)$$

Power consumption is evaluated from empirical equations based on three dimensionless numbers: the power number (N_p), the impeller-imposed Reynolds number Re_{imp} and the Froude number Fr, defined as follows:

$$N_p = P / (\rho_L n^3 d_{imp}^5) \quad (34)$$

$$\text{Re}_{imp} = \rho_L n d_{imp}^2 / \mu_L \quad (35)$$

$$\text{Fr} = d_{imp} n^2 / g. \quad (36)$$

Here, n represents the rotational speed of the impeller.

Stirring has been shown to have a key influence on reaction rate [32]. Currently, no information is available on the advised correlation between rotational speed and reactor size. Since laboratory tests are carried out on small samples, it is reasonable to assume that the actual stirring conditions could be characterised by a low rotational speed (10.0–16.6 Hz is advised by Wan et al. [32]) to limit the tip velocity.

As such, the rotational speed was evaluated by imposing a supercritical regime, defined as the transition between non-aerated (subcritical) and aerated (supercritical) conditions:

$$n_{cr} = (S/K)^{\frac{7}{10}} (\mu_L/\rho_L)^{\frac{1}{21}} g^{\frac{10}{21}} d_{imp}^{-\frac{4}{7}} \quad (37)$$

As seen from Eq. 37, it is safe to assume a reduced required rotational speed as the size of the system increases. The critical rotational speed n_{cr} is also a function of the liquid thermophysical properties and the type of impeller,

Table 1

Input parameters for the HTR assessment.

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
Net energy content E	5 kWh	System efficiency η	45 %
Reaction heat ΔH_r	50.6 kJ/mol	Activation energy E_a	121.0 kJ/mol
Kinetic rate k_0	$2.61 \times 10^{12} \text{ min}^{-1}$	Pressure coefficient b	-1.397 bar^{-1}
Initial DoH	95 %	Target DoH	20 %
Max H ₂ content	5.81 w %	Reactor AR	1.7
Initial temperature	473 K	Hydrogen pressure	1.0 bar
External fluid inlet temperature $T_f^{T_{des}}$	473 K	External fluid mass flow rate \dot{m}_f	0.718 kg/s

with S and K being empirical parameters (for the Half Hold-up impeller, $K = 13.5$, $S = 9.5$). Therefore, the power consumption is deduced from Eq. 34, with the power number evaluated as the minimum value resulting from Eqs. 38 and 39, valid for $500 < \text{Re}_{imp} < 250000$:

$$N_p = K \text{Re}_{imp}^{-0.3} \quad (38)$$

$$N_p = S (\text{Re}_{imp} \text{Fr})^{-1/3}. \quad (39)$$

2.2.3. Thermophysical properties

DowthermTM Q properties are evaluated using CoolProp libraries [33]. Since no reliable and comprehensive database is currently available for the main thermophysical properties of NEC (namely density ρ_l , viscosity μ_l , specific heat capacity c_l , and thermal conductivity λ_l), a group-contribution method was implemented [34].

Dynamic viscosity, density, and specific heat capacity have been evaluated with the Joback method, while thermal conductivity values are based on Gharagheizi. Both modelling procedures provide a reasonable estimate for organic liquids, assuming a temperature-dependent behaviour; methodology and data are taken from Green and Perry [34, Section 2].

The overall binary mixture made out of the fully loaded and unloaded carrier is then characterised by assuming a mass-weighted average for c_l (Eq. 40), the effective mass-to-volume ratio for ρ_l (Eq. 41), Gambill's method for μ_l (Eq. 42) [35], and Vredeveld's for λ_l (Eq. 43) [36].

$$c_l = \sum_i x_{m,i} c_i \quad (40)$$

$$\rho_l = \left(\sum_i x_{m,i} / \rho_i \right)^{-1} \quad (41)$$

$$(\mu_l / \rho_l)^{-1/3} = \sum_i x_{m,i} \nu_i^{-1/3} \quad (42)$$

$$\lambda_l = \left(\sum_i x_{m,i} \lambda_i^{-2} \right)^{-1/2} \quad (43)$$

With $x_{m,i}$ being the mass fraction of the component in the mixture and ν_i the kinematic viscosity.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Heat Transfer Ratio analysis

The optimisation process was led by introducing a non-linear condition over the Heat Transfer Ratio to optimise the heat transfer process.

To this end, the impact of HTR on reactor performance was first assessed, using the parameters listed in Table 1.

The net amount of hydrogen stored in the reactor is obtained from its net energy content E , the efficiency of the system η , and hydrogen HHV: $m_{\text{H}_2} = E / (\eta \text{HHV})$.

Figure 2: DoH and temperature profile over time for different efficacy levels.

Fig. 2 shows the influence of the Heat Transfer Ratio on operating times. Although no actual bound is given for the latter since faster releases are not necessarily required nor preferred, control through poorer heat transfer performances should be avoided.

The different discharged hydrogen content is clearly a result of different temperature trends. With higher HTR values, the temperature drop for a given system progressively decreases. Consequently, faster kinetics are ensured and a lower degree of hydrogenation is achieved by the 180 min mark, by which a 0.2 DoH threshold is reached using NEC or DBT as carriers (Fig. 2 shows the behaviour of a reactor based on NEC). As the gap between different temperature profiles is reduced and the overall temperature does not stray far from the original design temperature T_{des} , the kinetic performance tends to a constant temperature trend, and only marginal improvements are possible. Further raising the HTR above about 100 for this system, either through a higher external fluid mass flow rate or more expensive design choices, would not lead to practical gains. In this way, a threshold value can be identified, which in this case is $HTR_{thr} \approx 100$.

The HTR parameter can be used to compare different LOHCs. For example, looking at the performance of NEC and DBT (Fig. 3), a threshold HTR value of about 90–100 is needed in both cases to achieve a final deviation lower than 5% with respect to the constant temperature release profile. Temperature levels are chosen by assuming a final $DoH(t = 180 \text{ min}) \approx 0.20$ at $p = 1.00 \text{ bar}$, corresponding to 473 and 583 K respectively for NEC and DBT.

Fig. 3 shows from left to right how the higher HTR decreases the final degree of hydrogenation asymptotically with respect to the performance of the constant temperature profile. As such, significant improvements are achieved only at low HTR values (≤ 100), above which the performance is already similar to those granted by a constant-temperature release scenario. Preliminary results for other carriers hint at a possible correlation between the reaction order and the threshold value.

Consistent with the lumped parameter approach and the definition of HTR, which is independent of size, both the scaling up and down of the sample leads to the same kinetic performance if the thermal efficacy is kept constant.

Figure 3: HTR influence over NEC and DBT systems. Dashed lines represent constant-temperature simulations. Left: DoH reached at $t = 180$ min for different values of HTR; right: deviation of the real reactor from the DoH reached in an ideal constant-temperature reactor.

For any given size, the greater the HTR, the more limited the temperature drop will be. Consequently, higher temperature levels enhance the kinetic performance of the system. Since a relatively high heat demand is the main drawback of LOHC-based systems, it is crucial to strike the right balance between energy costs and release kinetics.

Only marginal kinetic improvements are achieved for higher values of the Heat Transfer Ratio, and, as such, a threshold value is defined to mark this saturation effect.

Although the actual best choice for the HTR_{thr} value might differ to account for specific operating conditions and control strategies, a threshold value of $HTR_{thr} = 100$ was used in this article, allowing for a deviation from the DoH reached in an ideal constant-temperature reactor $\Delta_{\%} DoH_{i,const T} \leq 5\%$.

It must be reiterated that HTR is intended to be a tool for assessing how close the actual kinetic performance of the system is to that of a constant-temperature sample. However, the amount of heat required is strictly correlated to the carrier itself and the reaction temperature: further and broader analyses are needed to optimise the efficiency of the whole system.

3.2. Heat transfer optimisation

The optimisation results displayed in Table 2 show that the half-pipe coiled reactor is a better solution in terms of energy savings due to a power requirement that is almost halved. The gap between the two options is likely to be even greater, since the power supply to the agitation nozzles was neglected.

These results indicate that in an LOHC system, the reactor can operate with little power and energy requirements. As a check of the consistency of the results, impeller power consumption was also evaluated with Nagata's correlations [37], obtaining a similar outcome.

Table 2 shows the same optimal AR value for the two layouts. This result is due to the greater contribution of the stirring power to the overall power consumption P , since it is mainly related to the diameter of the stirrer. A slightly lower P is required to operate the coiled reactor since better heat performances can be achieved: as such, a higher mass flow rate is required for the jacketed reactor.

Furthermore, to achieve the target HTR, both the jacket width and the diameter of the pipes are set at the upper limit of their variability range. In contrast, the optimal pitch value could actually be replaced by an optimal range (as seen in Figs. 4 and 5) correlated with the same number of pipes.

Running local optimisation processes shows that similar results can be reached with multiple parameter combinations. Consequently, if additional constraints on heat transfer efficacy or other aspects such as material usage and

Table 2

Results of the reactor optimisation process.

Parameter	Jacketed reactor	Half-pipe coiled reactor
	Value	Value
Height H	39.22 cm	39.22 cm
Inner diameter D_i	9.81 cm	9.81 cm
Outer diameter D_e	11.21 cm	11.21 cm
Aspect ratio AR	4.00	4.00
External fluid speed	2.05 m/s	2.40 m/s
External fluid mass flow rate \dot{m}_f	16.97 kg/s	16.12 kg/s
Power consumption P	2.3 W	0.9 W
Jacket width t	5.0 cm	-
Pipes diameter d	-	10.16 cm
Pipes pitch s	-	4.93 cm
Overall heat transfer coefficient U	6.21 kW K ⁻¹ m ⁻²	6.38 kW K ⁻¹ m ⁻²
HTR	100.0	100.0

Figure 4: Influence of different parameters on heat transfer

volume, or both, were to be introduced, different choices might be best suited. Therefore, those alternative designs would not significantly impact the energy demand of the system and the overall storage efficiency.

Increasing the size of the system requires further analysis since large-scale batch reactors may not be commercially available or sufficiently effective in terms of overall efficiency. Therefore, additional requirements should also take into account parallel reactor configurations.

A sensitivity analysis was run to evaluate each parameter's influence over the Heat Transfer Ratio and the power requirements, varying each parameter in its range while setting the others to their optimal value.

Fig. 4 shows that for a set value of the other parameters, both AR and the diameter of the pipes have a great influence on the actual efficacy of the heat transfer process. On the contrary, due to the limited variability for the set size of the reactor, the pitch has a limited impact on the final outcome. On the other hand, the velocity of the external fluid v is the most important parameter, with the Heat Transfer Ratio displaying an almost linear dependency. In fact, higher velocities lead to both a higher mass flow rate and better convection.

Increasing the velocity, aspect ratio, or diameter of the pipes leads to better performance. On the other hand, increasing the pitch reduces HTR as long as a smaller number of pipes fits the batch height.

Figure 5: Influence of the different parameters on the power consumption with respect to its optimal value.

Fig. 5 reaffirms the importance of AR and d on the resulting power requirements, with discontinuities arising due to the number of pipes being an integer value. The pitch has a more limited influence, while v still has the most significant impact on the final result in the same way as explained in the previous paragraph.

Combining this result with Fig. 2 leads to a key finding: Increasing heat transfer to maintain a constant temperature is both pointless and highly detrimental in terms of power consumption, as the most reliable way to increase HTR is through the velocity of the external fluid. As such, even for suboptimal geometric configurations, limited variability in the energy costs is expected.

4. Conclusions

Reactors are key elements in LOHC-based systems. This paper provides a streamlined design procedure to optimise two types of batch reactors using a lumped-parameter approach.

The lumped-parameter model is effective enough to guide the preliminary design stage, and the optimisation process leads to minimising the system's power consumption while still granting the optimum heat transfer efficacy. Different objectives could also be featured in the optimisation phase, such as material minimisation, volume reduction, and different definitions of heat transfer effectiveness, here taken into account through the introduction of the Heat Transfer Ratio. This parameter is based on the flow heat capacity of the external fluid, the heat transfer effectiveness, and the maximum heat rate required by the LOHC dehydrogenation reaction.

This parameter only needs to reach a certain threshold value and is not to be maximised since no further kinetic improvements would be achieved once the threshold value is reached. Although HTR values higher than the threshold do not significantly improve the thermodynamic performance, the associated working conditions would most likely require a higher external fluid velocity with a marked increase in power consumption.

The significant number of different parameter combinations that satisfy the effectiveness lower bound with similar energy requirements hints at relatively flexible conditions, and additional constraints could likely be included without hindering the system's performance.

This design strategy could be applied to other reactor types (such as PFRs), although the lumped-parameter hypothesis would need to be tested again. Fast and simple implementation of dedicated components in object-based programming languages will then be possible, allowing for a straightforward analysis of complex energy systems, including dynamic simulation and control strategies.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Marco Gambini: Validation, Visualisation. **Federica Guarnaccia:** Conceptualisation, Methodology, Software, Validation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualisation. **Michele Manno:** Conceptualisation, Methodology, Validation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualisation, Supervision. **Michela Vellini:** Validation, Visualisation.

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